

Balimau Putih, cultivar tolerant of rice tungro-associated viruses

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Rice cultivar Balimau Putih (IRRI Acc. no. 17204) consistently showed tungro resistance in greenhouse mass-screening tests. Its resistance to rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses was further evaluated by test tube inoculation and compared with resistance of susceptible TN1.

Seven-day-old seedlings, 120 for each variety, were infested with green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* (5

insects/seedling) that had 4 d access to TN1 plants infected with both RTBV and RTSV. Presence of tungro-associated viruses was detected by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) of each plant 1 mo after inoculation. The relative amount of virus was determined by ELISA (absorbance value at 405 nm) at 2, 6, and 10 wk after inoculation. Height and yield were measured.

Balimau Putih was more susceptible to infection with tungro-associated viruses than TN1 (see table) but did not show symptoms typical of RTBV and RTBV+RTSV infection. Relative amounts of RTBV and RTSV were consistently lower in Balimau (see figure). Apparently, the multiplication of tungro-associated viruses was

tolerable. Height reduction due to infection was lower in Balimau Putih than in TN1. Balimau Putih also had lower yield reductions. □

Reaction of Balimau Putih and TN1 in RTBV and RTSV by test tube inoculation of RTBV and RTSV at 5 insects^a per seedling. IRRI, 1986.

Variety	Plants (no.) infected with ^b			Healthy plants (no.)	Infection (%)	Height reduction (%)		Yield reduction (%)	
	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV			RTBV	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTBV+RTSV
TN1	87	31	0	8	93.6	41.6	21.3	90.0	50.0
Balimau Putih	46	68	3	5	95.9	11.4	5.0	18.4	1.6

^aGreen leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* were given 4 d access to TN1 plants infected with both RTBV and RTSV. ^bTotal of 4 trials. Detected by ELISA.

Relative amounts of RTBV and RTSV in doubly infected TN1 and Balimau Putih. IRRI, 1986.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

An approach to develop gall midge (GM)-resistant rice strains

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The GM *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) is being successfully tackled through conventional breeding using major genes from known resistant donors. Some parents, like IR20 and Pelita 1/1, although susceptible, were known to possess both duplicate and complementary genes for GM resistance. The approach exploits these duplicate and complementary genes to

develop GM-resistant, high yielding cultures.

Progeny from crosses involving IR20 and two other susceptible parents (Zenith, Malagkit Sungsong) were studied. During 1975–80, single plant

progeny from F₃ to F₆ were selected under high insect pressure artificially created in the field. From 1981, single plants selected for high resistance, with semidwarf habit and other desirable agronomic traits, were bulked in F₇ and

Performance of promising GM-resistant cultures at Cuttack, India.

Designation	Cross combination ^a	Silvershoots (%)				Yield (t/ha)			Grain type ^b
		1981	1982	1983	1984	1982	1983	1984	
CR294-28-1	IR20/Zenith//MSS	1.5	0.1	1.3	0.7	3.9	4.1	3.9	LS
CR294-548	IR20/Zenith//MSS	2.6	nil	1.1	nil	4.4	4.3	4.1	LS
CR316-639	IR20/MSS	2.3	0.1	1.6	nil	4.2	4.1	4.2	LB
CR318-548-7	IR20/MSS//Zenith	1.2	nil	1.2	nil	4.0	4.2	3.6	LB
Jaya	Susceptible standard	51.1	16.6	26.6	25.8	3.1	3.1	3.0	LB
IR36	Resistant standard	1.8	0.6	1.3	nil	3.7	4.1	4.1	LS

^aMSS = Malagkit sungsong. ^bLS = long slender, LB = long bold.

field evaluated for yield potential and GM resistance.

Field trials led to the identification of 4 cultures (2 from CR294, 1 from CR316, 1 from CR318) of 125 to 130 d duration with high resistance to GM (see table). All cultures also possess good levels of field resistance to bacterial leaf blight. They are being tested under the All India Coordinated multilocation testing in GM problem areas. Preliminary data of 1984 kharif showed that CR294-548 (IET9233) was resistant at the three sites of high GM incidence (Mangalore, Raipur, Sakoli). Average yield was outstanding in both the three high-incidence locations and in the nine test locations.

Tailoring GM resistance by exploiting the duplicate and complementary genes from IR20 might possibly counter the increasing spectrum and admixtures of GM biotypes. $\mathcal{J}$

Sources of resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and green leafhopper (GLH)

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We evaluated 100 rice accessions received through IRWBPHN 85 for resistance to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera*. The 15 accessions identified as resistant were further evaluated for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens* by the standard seedbox screening.

Pregerminated seeds were sown in 60-x 40- x 10-cm seedboxes; Ptb 33 and TN1 served as resistant and susceptible checks. Separate seedboxes were used for each hopper species. Each accession was replicated five times for each insect species.

Each seedling was infested with 8 2d-instar nymphs of WBPH and 5 2d-instar nymphs of GLH 7 d after sowing. Damage was rated when 90-100% of TN1 plants died.

All 15 accessions were resistant to WBPH and to GLH (see table). $\square$

Reaction of rice varieties, cultures, and mutants to yellow stem borer (YSB) in Kerala

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Activity of the YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) was studied on 24 rice varieties, cultures, and mutants in 1984 kharif and 26 in 1985 kharif.

Entries were grown in 20-m² plots replicated 3 times. Incidence of deadhearts 45 d after transplanting and incidence of whiteheads 10 d before harvest were recorded and damage percentage was calculated.

In 1984, deadheart incidence was highest in culture 1907 and lowest in culture 4. The highest number of whiteheads was in TKM9 and the lowest in culture 52-3-6.

In 1985, the incidence of deadhearts was highest in culture 4-4 and TKM9 and lowest in culture 126. The highest number of whiteheads was recorded in culture 4-4 and the lowest in Triveni (see table). $\square$

Rice resistance to WBPH and GLH. TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1985.

Designation	Damage rating ^a	
	WBPH	GLH
Chempan	1 a	1 a
Chempan pandi	3 b	1 a
Horonamawee	1 a	1 a
IR9852-22-3	1 a	1 a
IR13427-40-2-3-3	1 a	1 a
IR13429-1961	1 a	1 a
IR13475-7-3-2	1 a	1 a
IR15429-268-1-2-1	3 b	1 a
IR15527-21-2-3	3 b	1 a
IR15529-256-1	3 b	1 a
IR15795-151-2-3-2-2	1 a	1 a
IR28154-101-3-2	1 a	1 a
Podiwi A8	3 b	1 a
Valsara Champara	1 a	1 a
Sufaida 172	1 a	1 a
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	1 a	1 a
TN1 (susceptible check)	9 c	9 b

^aMean of 5 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

YSB incidence in rice in Kerala, India, 1984 and 1985 kharif.^a

Variety	Deadhearts (%)		Whiteheads (%)	
	1984	1985	1984	1985
Jyothi	1.0 (1.2)	0.2 (0.8)	7.3 (2.7)	5.6 (2.3)
Jaya	0.7 (1.1)	0.4 (1.0)	3.9 (1.9)	14.1 (3.8)
MO 5	0.2 (0.8)	0.1 (0.8)	6.0 (2.2)	10.0 (3.1)
MO 6	0.4 (1.0)	0.1 (0.8)	12.2 (3.5)	7.4 (2.6)
TKM 9	0.7 (1.1)	0.6 (1.0)	36.2 (5.9)	20.1 (4.5)
IR36	0.2 (0.8)	0.5 (1.0)	7.3 (2.6)	13.0 (3.6)
IR50	0.2 (0.8)	0.1 (0.8)	4.5 (2.2)	13.3 (3.5)
<i>Culture</i>				
1907	1.3 (1.3)	0.3 (0.9)	9.5 (3.1)	9.1 (3.0)
1954	0.3 (0.9)	0.2 (0.8)	4.5 (1.9)	10.5 (3.2)
43-1-4	0.2 (0.9)	0.3 (0.9)	5.5 (2.4)	10.7 (3.2)
52-3-6 ^b	0.1 (0.8)	0.4 (0.9)	2.7 (1.4)	9.7 (3.1)
25337	0.3 (0.9)	0.2 (0.8)	7.4 (2.5)	7.4 (2.6)
169 ^b	0.5 (1.0)	0.2 (0.8)	12.1 (3.5)	5.1 (2.3)
25331	0.3 (0.9)	0.3 (0.9)	9.0 (2.7)	15.2 (3.9)
4 ^b	0.1 (0.8)	0.3 (0.9)	4.6 (2.0)	13.1 (3.6)
1537/2	0.2 (0.9)	0.2 (0.9)	5.2 (2.1)	7.1 (2.7)
(Karthika)	0.2 (0.8)	0.0 (0.7)	10.3 (2.8)	6.3 (2.5)
126	0.2 (0.8)	0.4 (0.7)	5.8 (2.8)	9.6 (2.5)
26-1-1	0.2 (0.8)	0.4 (0.9)	5.7 (2.4)	20.4 (3.0)
4-4	0.2 (0.8)	0.4 (0.9)	5.7 (2.3)	20.4 (4.5)
<i>Mutant</i>				
6	0.3 (0.9)	0.3 (0.9)	17.8 (4.0)	17.8 (4.0)
210	0.2 (0.8)	0.1 (0.8)	11.5 (3.3)	12.4 (3.5)
2	0.3 (0.9)	0.2 (0.9)	13.8 (3.7)	15.0 (2.4)
102 ^b	0.4 (1.0)	0.1 (0.8)	6.6 (2.6)	5.6 (2.4)
109	0.2 (0.8)	0.3 (0.9)	9.5 (3.1)	13.7 (3.3)
Cul. 23332-2	-	0.2 (0.8)	-	13.2 (3.6)
Triveni ^b	-	0.3 (0.8)	-	5.0 (2.2)
CD at 5% level	0.2	0.2	1.3	1.2

^aFigures in parentheses are square root transformation values. ^bLess susceptible to stem borer incidence.